

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Assessing the viability of blade-integrated sensors for collision detection and mitigation

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Abstract

The risk of collision between a moving component of a tidal turbine and marine organisms, particularly marine mammals, has been identified as a key concern associated with tidal energy development, and has delayed permitting processes due to a lack of pertinent data. While few collisions have been observed in deployments to date and modeling efforts indicate that collision may not be fatal to the animal, there is still a nonzero chance of collision, and it remains difficult to gather empirical data on turbine collisions. Existing turbine blades have been instrumented with strain gauges to monitor the blade's structural health; here, we investigate if they can also detect collisions with marine fauna. Strain gauges are mounted on a laboratory-scale cross-flow turbine blade and silicone marine mammal models are used to simulate collisions in a flume. The results show that the collected strain data can be used to reliably detect a head-on collision as well as quantify its impact, and, through additional filtering, small collisions can be detected as well. Analysis of the strain data also reveals patterns that could be useful for determining when an animal passes close to a blade (i.e., near miss). Further experimentation is needed to fully characterize the blade-integrated sensors and to determine whether near misses are detectable.

Keywords: integrated instrumentation; collision risk; collision detection; environmental impacts of marine energy

1. Introduction

Quantifying and/or reducing the potential risk of underwater turbine collision could positively impact the viability of widespread tidal turbine deployment, as the perceived level of collision risk often hinders permitting processes. The field needs more information on the frequency of collisions and a more comprehensive understanding of the consequences of these collisions. Because empirical data on collisions are limited and challenging to gather, collision risk remains a key regulatory concern. Data to inform collision risk are typically gathered using optical cameras, acoustic cameras, or echosounders [8]. Each sensing method has advantages and disadvantages, but they all are limited in their abilities to distinguish between collisions and near misses. Furthermore, these sensors cannot quantify the force of an impact, making it difficult to determine the potential harm to the animal, and data analysis for these sensors is cost- and labor-intensive [2,5]. Previous studies have assessed the avoidance behavior of certain fish and marine mammal species around turbines both in the field and in the laboratory [7,9], which has informed collision risk models

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that predict the probability of a collision occurring although they are still lacking in empirical data for validation [1]. While available data suggest that in most scenarios [4], the risk of collision is relatively low, there is still a nonzero chance for collision, and for sensitive species these potential collisions could impact individuals and thus populations. Development of a reliable, low-cost method to detect and quantify collisions between marine fauna and turbine blades could reduce the uncertainty surrounding collision risk.

Strain gauges have been integrated into turbine blades to monitor blade structural health [6]. Here, we explore whether these sensors can be used to detect collision events or near misses at the laboratory scale. Silicone marine mammal models collide with a cross-flow turbine in a flume to reproduce the structural dynamics present during a collision. When the silicone model collides with the turbine, the resulting strain is measured and used to determine the force of collision. The experimental set-up and preliminary testing are described in this paper. Results including analysis of the collision strain profiles and an evaluation of experimental set-up are subsequently discussed. Our primary objective is to evaluate the technical feasibility of strain gauge-based collision detection and make future design recommendations. We do not attempt to scale laboratory results to assess the impacts of collisions in situ.

2. Methodology

2.1. Instrumented turbine assembly

The cross-flow turbine used for our experiments is shown in Fig. 1.b. This turbine has two straight blades connected to a central shaft by two disc struts. The aluminum blades have a NACA 0018 profile with a chord length of 0.0406 m. The disc struts mount the turbine blades with an 8° pitch angle. The turbine has a diameter of 0.172 m and a span of 0.24 m. The turbine blades can be considered beams with fixed supports on either end. A head-on collision induces bending strain in the blade. To measure this bending strain, four linear strain gauges are mounted directly on one of the blades to construct a full Wheatstone bridge bending circuit. Hereafter, we refer to this blade as the “instrumented blade,” and the blade without strain gauges as the “non-instrumented blade.” Each face of the instrumented blade has two strain gauges that are coated with epoxy to prevent corrosion and physical damage. The strain gauge signal wires are secured along the turbine to a waterproof enclosure that is mounted on the shaft above the water surface. The waterproof enclosure houses a Mantracourt T24-SAfi strain transmitter module, which collects strain measurements on demand and wirelessly transmits them to a computer base station at a rate of 2 kHz.

2.2. Flume set-up

The experiments described in this work were conducted in the Alice C. Tyler Flume in the Harris Hydraulics Laboratory at the University of Washington. The flume has a rectangular test section that is 3.7 m long and 0.76 m wide with a maximum fill depth of 0.60 m and was operated at the maximum flow speed of approximately 1.1 m/s. A performance characterization was run with the instrumented turbine to determine the optimal tip-speed ratio ($\lambda = 2.0$).

Fig. 1. (a) Flume test section showing turbine and alignment tube placement; (b) Cross-flow turbine; strain gauges not shown in CAD assembly.

This tip-speed ratio was used for all subsequent experiments to create a realistic scenario of what would happen in a field setting. Prior to conducting collisions, strain measurements were collected while the turbine was operating at the optimal tip-speed ratio to determine the background strain values during normal turbine operation.

Fig. 1.a shows a CAD rendering of the full experimental set-up. A horizontal alignment tube was used to ensure a straight and consistent travel path for the silicone model. The turbine is placed in the center of the flume's test section with the center of the alignment tube positioned 0.91 m (3 ft) upstream. The silicone models were inserted manually into the alignment tube and the flume current propelled the model in a straight line directly toward the turbine. The depth of the alignment tube was adjusted such that the model would collide with the blade beneath the strain gauges to avoid direct contact with them.

2.3. Marine mammal models

The silicone marine mammal models used in this experiment (Fig. 2) were designed and fabricated at Pacific Northwest National Laboratory. The whale models were made from flexible platinum cure silicone and manufactured using a four-part mold. The mold was 3D printed and designed with a pouring opening for the silicone. To control density, glass bubbles were incorporated into the silicone. The model dimensions were scaled to be approximately representative of the size of an orca (*Orcinus orca*). The models were ballasted to be approximately neutrally buoyant and instrumented with accelerometers to provide a secondary measurement of collisions, though these data are not presented here. Accelerometer instrumentation was identical to those used in Sensor Fish [3] designed to study fish passage through hydroelectric dams.

2.4. Collision experiments

Marine mammal models were released in the flume a total of 70 times: 47 with the alignment tube centered in the flume and 23 with the alignment tube positioned at the edge of the turbine diameter. With the alignment tube positioned in the center, there was a collision every time, though not always with the instrumented blade. Therefore, the alignment tube was moved off-center to simulate near misses where the whale model passed close by the turbine without contact in order to evaluate whether variable hydrodynamics due to the presence of the model could be detected with the strain gauges. It proved more difficult to simulate successful near miss collisions because turbulence caused by the instrumented blade's surface influenced the whale model's travel.

For each collision, a separate strain file was generated and subsequently formatted and plotted to produce a strain versus time profile. In addition, a video of each collision was recorded for comparison with the strain profiles.

Fig. 2. Silicone whale model used for collision experiments shown from multiple angles.

3. Results

3.1. Interpreting strain profile

Table 1 summarizes the rates of collisions with the instrumented blade, non-instrumented blade, and no interaction.

Table 1. Summary of the occurrences of collision types as a result of the alignment tube location.

Alignment Tube Location	Instrumented Blade Strikes (%)	Non-instrumented Blade Strikes (%)	Misses (%)
Centered	59.6	40.4	0
Offset	17.4	8.7	73.9

Fig. 3.a shows the strain profile for one representative collision with the instrumented blade. Positive strain values indicate when the instrumented blade is in tension (when the outer surface is facing upstream). Correspondingly, negative strain values indicate when the instrumented blade is facing downstream. The additional oscillation present in downstream strain values is thought to be caused by turbulence from the turbine assembly. There is a clear spike in the strain profile indicating a collision with the instrumented blade since it is positioned upstream. Impacts with the non-instrumented blade result in a spike in negative strain (when the instrumented blade is downstream). In this collision, the whale model approached the turbine head-on and collided with the leading edge of the instrumented blade. A slight dip in strain values can be seen preceding the impact, suggesting the presence of the whale model is blocking the current thereby lessening the fluid force acting on the blade.

This pattern can be further examined in Fig. 3.b, which shows the strain profile for a collision with the non-instrumented blade. In this collision, the whale model approaches the turbine head-on when the instrumented blade is facing upstream then the nose hits the front face of the non-instrumented blade. The whale model is knocked back from the force of impact then is pushed forward by the flume current when the tail blocks the flow in front of the instrumented blade. When the whale model passes the turbine, the strain measurements return to normal behavior.

3.2. Data analysis

Qualitative analysis of the collected data, including video and strain profile comparison, suggests that while relatively low-impact collisions were detectable, near misses were not. We used a high-pass filter to eliminate the sinusoidal strain signal resulting from turbine rotation to determine if there are underlying peaks or patterns that would indicate an oncoming interaction. Fig. 4 shows the comparison of the raw strain signal with the filtered strain signal.

Fig. 3. (a) Representative head-on collision with instrumented blade, the spike indicates the maximum impact; (b) Collision with non-instrumented blade. The yellow regions are when the whale model is near the instrumented blade, partially blocking the fluid force. The red outlined peak is the negative spike corresponding to the impact with the non-instrumented blade, and the green outlined peak corresponds to the regular strain experienced by the instrumented blade when the whale model is knocked back. Note that the scale of the y-axis varies between subplots.

Fig. 4. Comparison of raw and filtered strain signal for low-impact collision example.

Collision 4 has similar dynamics to the collision discussed in the previous section (Fig. 3.b), and while no discernable spikes are seen in the raw signal in Fig. 4, the filtered signal shows a clear peak confirming the impact that was seen in the video for the collision. Applying this same technique to the near miss collision data did not reveal any change in the signal to indicate interaction.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

The results from the experiments discussed in this work demonstrate that blade-integrated strain gauges can be used to reliably detect collisions under ideal conditions. These preliminary results motivate further experiments to understand the limitations of this approach. First, the collected data indicates that near misses are not detectable with the current set-up, but this can be explained by considering the type of collisions we would expect to see in this scenario. When the whale model passes around the outside of the turbine, we would expect a collision when the blades are positioned in-line with the fluid flow, where the relative strain would be near zero and a block in fluid flow would not be detectable. In order to better study near misses, more experiments should be conducted with different launching placements or securing the whale model in a stationary position upstream or downstream of the turbine to better observe the change in strain measurements.

Second, all experiments were conducted at the flume's fastest water velocity; this parameter could be varied to determine the minimum detectable force of impact with the whale model. A lower flume speed could also reveal more variability in strain measurements as the silicone model approaches the turbine. Finally, in the experiments described here, the strain gauges are mounted directly on the turbine blade surface, creating roughness that induced more turbulence around the turbine, reducing its performance, and likely influenced the strain readings. A more refined design with embedded strain gauges and lead wires would likely be more representative of field conditions.

Qualitative analysis of the strain measurements reveals patterns in the strain response as the whale model approaches and collides with the blade. This motivates the development of automated approaches to detect collisions, predict oncoming collisions, or determine what type of collision occurred. For example, the shape and magnitude of the strain during the time window of impact, the force of impact, and the duration of impact could be used to train a machine learning algorithm to distinguish between the different types of collisions that occur. In the future, this type of algorithm could inform the development of turbine hardware or control algorithms that either prevent or lessen the severity of collisions.

Acknowledgements

This work is part of the Triton Initiative supported by the United States Department of Energy's Water Power Technologies Office. The authors are grateful for the assistance of Greg Talpey in turbine performance characterization and turbine data collection during experiments and Daniel Deng, Jayson Martinez, and Aljon Salalila

for design and manufacturing of the marine mammal models. The authors also thank Kate Van Ness, Abigail Snortland, and Brian Polagye for productive conversations about these experiments.

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